

Creativity Expectations of Leaders and Radical Creativity Through Creative Efficacy of Employees: The Mediating Role of Leaders' Paradoxical Behaviour

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Abstract

Background: Studies show that leaders play a crucial role in shaping employees' behavioural patterns and creativity in the workplace. However, the relationship between leadership and radical creativity is complex but not clearly understood.

Objective: The study explores how leaders' creativity expectations impact workers' radical creativity, examining creative self-efficacy and leaders' paradoxical behaviour in workload pressure and radical innovation

Methodology: The study employed a cross-sectional research design, collecting data from personnel in the Human Resources and Research & Development departments of major industrial enterprises within Bangladesh's Export Processing Zones. A total of 340 respondents participated, comprising 62 supervisors and 278 employees. To ensure the model's validity, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted to assess model fit, while Hierarchical Linear Modelling (HLM) was utilised to test the proposed hypotheses. Additionally, a multilevel moderated mediation model was applied to analyse the final results.

Results: The results demonstrate that leaders' creativity expectations (LCE) positively affect creative self-efficacy (CSE) and radical creativity, particularly when leaders display elevated levels of paradoxical behaviour (PLB) and workers experience substantial workload pressure. The findings suggest that manufacturing firms can advance by leveraging the creative self-efficacy of both employees and leaders.

Conclusion: Creative self-efficacy requires not just encouraging radical innovation but also navigating the contradictory hurdles inherent in substantial creative pursuits.

Unique contribution: This study provides empirical evidence that leaders' creativity expectations (LCE) and paradoxical leader behaviour (PLB), which integrate performance expectations with autonomy and constraints with flexibility, can enhance employees' creative self-efficacy (CSE) and radical creativity, particularly under conditions of high workload pressure.

Key Recommendation: Leaders should create a workplace environment that fosters guidance and encourages employees to share their ideas.

Keywords: Creativity expectations, Radical creativity, Creative efficacy, Paradoxical behaviour

Introduction

Organisational creativity starts with innovative thinking and proactive efforts by individuals. Creativity involves employees utilising talents, know-how, and experience to generate thoughts that solve problems, make decisions, and effectively complete tasks. Recent theories classify innovation into incremental and radical creativity (Gilson & Madjar, 2011). Previous research indicates that factors like creative coworkers, organisational identity, and external support are stronger predictors of incremental creativity. On the other hand, radical creativity is more dependent on employees' willingness to take risks, strategic leadership, and a focus on innovation and motivation. (Regts et al., 2019). Research has established the leader as one of the actors in the social background that can shape such employee comportment. Given the complexity of creativity and the various ways leaders can influence employee performance, it's crucial to understand the intricate connections between leadership and radical creativity in the workplace. While previous research has helped build an initial understanding of supervisors' role in fostering employee creativity, several key questions about the supervisor-employee creativity relationship remain unanswered from an empirical standpoint.

For example, while leaders' expectations are important for radical creative work, it is not clear how these expectations form the radical creative performance of employees. Furthermore, while we know that monitoring practices affect the creativity of the workplace, what drives supervisors to direct innovative actions towards certain workers and not towards others is not clear (Tierney & Farmer, 2004). Supervisors need answers to these questions to successfully encourage radical creative efforts in the workplace, which were the basis of the current study. Given the importance

of this effect for contemporary businesses, more studies between supervisors and employees in high-pressure jobs are required to examine this process (Newman et al., 2018). The Pygmalion effect suggests that success brings greater difficulty and vulnerability, for example, gradual innovation (Tierney & Farmer, 2004).

Previous research indicates that, in order to start and maintain creative efforts, individuals must feel effective in their skills in creative activities (Walia, 2019). Research indicates that Creative Self-Efficacy (CSE) plays a vital role in predicting creativity expectations (Farmer & Tierney, 2017). Additionally, CSE serves as an important mediator between situational and personal factors, encompassing different leadership styles and innovative results. Nevertheless, there is a scarcity of studies exploring the factors that enhance radical creativity through creative self-efficacy in highly demanding circumstances (Farmer & Tierney, 2017). The application of the Pygmalion method in this study on employee innovation aims to contribute significantly to both theory and practice. Firstly, by building on a theoretical framework that combines the literature on employee radical creativity with the Pygmalion effect, this research offers a substantial integrative theoretical advancement. This integration helps address several unresolved questions and gaps present in both Pygmalion and creativity research. Secondly, this combined Pygmalion perspective sheds light on how supervisors can influence radical creativity, an area that has not been adequately explored in previous studies on creativity. It suggests connections between leaders' creativity expectations, their paradoxical attitudes, and the resulting effectiveness and efficiency in fostering innovation. Although a previous study (Hughes et al., 2018) discussed the correlation between supervisors' creativity and employees' creativity. Existing studies did not suggest how these expectations contributed to the radical innovative success.

Research questions:

1. How is an employee's radical creativity influenced by their leader's creativity expectations through creative self-efficacy?
2. Do leaders' paradoxical behaviour and employees' workload pressure moderate the process of radical creativity?

Theory and Hypothesis Development

The vast majority of the research on non-educational Pygmalion was done in military environments (Chen et al., 2019; Eden, 1982), or based on jobless or trainee. The one study carried out by sales associates in a typical corporate context critically discusses this model. In a creative sense, this model shows that the managers' creativity expectations for employees are related to the radical creative success of employees through creative self-efficacy (Hu et al., 2018). The flow of the model indicates that the level of creativity requirements of managers can dictate the degree to which they direct creativity support actions to employees. Such behaviours, which influence their radical creative output, are important in determining employee' decisions about their creative self-efficacy. As indicated previously, the current model also places a new aspect, paradoxical actions of leaders, and pressure to work that moderates the expectations of leaders and employee productivity in relation to radical innovation.

Leaders' Creativity expectations and Employee Radical creativity

Workers' radical imagination fosters radical innovation, which enables organisations to rapidly attain a dominant or monopolistic position in the market and redefine core competition. Recent research also reveals that a different tradition lies in radical innovation and gradual creativity. Innovative coworkers, organisational traits, and external motivation have been shown to have a greater impact on incremental innovation. In contrast, radical creativity is more influenced by strategic leadership, information networks, a willingness to take risks, and employees' intrinsic motivation.

The "Pygmalion Effect" suggests that their perceptions of creativity shape the extent to which leaders foster imagination in their followers. According to the expectation theory, leaders set altered creativity potentials based on followers' beliefs in both the role itself and their role in shaping it. This helps them focus their mental resources on creative thinking and unlock their full creative potential. Secondly, the existing literature has not examined how to foster a strong sense of team identity, which motivates members to collaborate toward a shared goal. Based on psychological contract theory (Ahmad, 2018), the basis of this partnership lies in whether the leader establishes innovative goals for their team members.

Leaders' creativity expectations and employees' creative self-efficacy

The significance of tools and role models in enabling activities, fostering collaboration among members, offering individualised assistance, and providing incentives that encourage individuals to establish creative objectives is crucial for enhancing creativity. In a laboratory environment (Yuan & Woodman, 2021), as well as in a field study (Tierney & Farmer, 2002), leaders who participated in more imaginative acts were encouraged to report on improved success in terms of their capacity to be creative in their work. However, if the employee does not interpret the supervisor's actions in this way, no significant change in effectiveness can be observed. While this connection is central to the Pygmalion effect and the possibility of an intermediate interpretive stage has been suggested, previous research has not determined whether employees' perceptions of their success are truly influenced by supervisory actions (Sabat et al., 2020).

The role of Paradoxical leaders' behaviour

Leaders face conflicting and paradoxical demands and challenges in competitive and diverse market environments. Leaders, therefore, must fulfil both institutional and organisational criteria that challenge the followers to illustrate equality, independence and versatility. Similarly, leaders need to manoeuvre through organisations and foster collaboration inherent in leadership activities while balancing consistency with the dynamic nature of climate change. PLB is described as "contradictory yet interrelated leading behaviour to meet concurrent demands for jobs simultaneously and over time"(Zhang et al., 2017).

Paradoxical leaders' behaviour and Creative self-efficacy

Individuals gather knowledge and information from their social environment to assess effectiveness (Bandura, 2018; Newman et al., 2019). Leader actions greatly affect employee performance, according to research. Social cognitive theory states that mastery experience, vicarious learning (or modelling), verbal persuasion, and physiological arousal build self-efficacy. Role modelling and expertise are crucial here. Paradoxical leaders should show staff how to handle

contradictory expectations in changing settings. As leaders model desirable actions, vicarious learning helps followers improve self-efficacy, according to study. Employees see and learn how to handle workplace disagreements when leaders behave ironically and effectively. Thus, workers become more self-efficacious while encountering contradictory creative problems.

Paradoxical leadership behaviour (PLB) can create a balanced work environment that supports mastery experiences by combining authority with autonomy-driven actions. While offering liberty and freedom, these leaders encourage staff to innovate and boost intrinsic drive (Ryan & Deci, 2020). Since PLB provides a positive atmosphere to handle creative tensions, employees may achieve success in creative results, which improves their CSE.

The role of workload pressure

PLB may theoretically improve the CSE of its workers, but the paradox theory is that PLB can prove more successful in cases where paradoxical tensions are important, such as workload strain (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017; Clark et al., 2020). This refers to the amount of work required within a given timeframe, including both the volume and speed of tasks, which is closely linked to time pressure. The effect of workload and time constraints on innovation is mixed. Some studies suggest a negative relationship between workload pressure and creativity (Li et al., 2021; Janssen, 2000). We propose that increased workload pressure heightens paradoxical tensions and that under high workloads, paradoxical leadership behaviour (PLB) becomes more crucial. As workload pressures increase, time and energy resources to achieve various objectives decrease, causing employees to face conflicts between competing demands and tasks (Tamannaefar & Motaghedifard, 2014). Paradoxical leadership behaviour (PLB) helps employees build creative self-efficacy (CSE). As a result, PLB becomes an important resource for managing conflicts that arise from workload pressure, ultimately fostering creativity (Schad et al., 2016). In situations where paradoxical strains are insignificant, PLB is mostly irrelevant and does not impact creative self-efficacy (CSE). Thus, there is a logical connection between high workload and the relevance of PLB to CSE.

Hypothesis 1: High paradoxical leadership behaviour and workload pressure amplify the positive effect of leadership creativity expectations on employees' creative self-efficacy.

2.6 The mediating role of Creative self-efficacy

Social cognitive theory posits that persons with diminished self-efficacy are inclined to evade tasks and exhibit less perseverance when confronted with adversities, while those with robust self-efficacy are more predisposed to exert more effort and maintain resilience in adversity (Koivisto & Hamari, 2019). Tierney and Farmer (2002) proposed that Core Self-Evaluations (CSE) serve as a primary incentive for participation in creative endeavours, with studies consistently associating creativity with CSE. Tierney and Farmer (2004) observed that persons who saw themselves as having superior creative ability were evaluated as more creative by their superiors. Moreover, Tierney and Farmer (2011) found that fluctuations in workers' core self-evaluations across time correlated with enhancements in their creative productivity. A meta-analysis by Liu et al. (2016) showed that CSE is a consistent predictor of inventive performance across several studies, irrespective of intrinsic and prosocial incentive components.

Hypothesis 2: CSE mediates LEC's indirect impact on radical creativity under high workload and PLB, enhancing creativity through positive self-evaluations.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Methodology

Sampling and Data Collection:

This study was carried out in the research and development departments of large manufacturing companies situated in the Dhaka Export Processing Zone. We search for full-functioning organisations which have every necessary department and are listed in the Bangladesh Economic Zone Authority. The researchers communicated with the HR and R&D departments and asked for permission to perform a survey of their employees. Fifteen (15) of them responded, and we selected five (5) of them based on our criteria. We select a purposive sampling technique. As such, the sample was drawn from five companies in Bangladesh that were prominent in their respective industries, encompassing readymade garments, power generation, software development, and healthcare companies. The average number of employees (population) was 9,553. Employees with permanent and full-time status and their Leaders participated in the survey.

Table 1: Research design

Target Population	Unit of analysis	Individual
	Sampling Unit	Employees and leaders
	Extent/ Area of research	Research & Development (R & Ds) of five manufacturing firms located in EPZ
	Time of data collection	November 2022- January 2023
Type of research	Quantitative	
Research tools	Two distinct set of structured questionnaires, for leaders and for employees	
Sampling Technique	Non-probability purposive sampling	
Data Used	Primary	
Sample Size	N= 340; 62 supervisors and 278 employees	
Analysis tool	Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method through using SPSS	

The study involved two sets of questionnaires targeting employees and their supervisors to examine various factors related to creativity in the workplace. Supervisors evaluated their employees' radical creativity, while employees provided assessments of their leaders' creativity expectations, paradoxical behaviours, creativity self-efficacy, and workload pressure. The survey, conducted in English, included 600 full-time workers, with 340 valid responses, yielding a 51% response rate, including input from 62 supervisors. Each work team comprised four employees reporting to one supervisor. On average, respondents were 35 years old (SD = 9.28) and had been with the company for 12.8 years (SD = 9.3). Both sets of data, from employees and supervisors, were utilized in the analysis, offering insights into the dynamics of creative performance within teams.

Table 2: Demographic Profile

Attributes	Option	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	221	65
	Female	119	35
Tenure	<5 years	68	20
	6-11 years	80	23.6
	12-17 years	192	56.4
Age	25-35 years	61.2	18
	36-46 years	176.8	52
	47-57 years	102	30
Education Level	Undergraduate	51	15
	Graduate	190.4	56
	Ph. D.	98.6	29
<i>Note: n= 340 employees</i>			

Variables and Measures

Measures from earlier studies were used in this study. The ratings on a 7-point Likert scale went from "1" (strongly disagree) to "7" (strongly agree). Each category was based on more than one item. Using a seven-point Likert scale, participants said whether they agreed or disagreed with four claims about how creative their bosses thought they were. The specific measurement scales for each variable are detailed below.

Table 3. Measurement Scales used in the research model

Constructs	Items	Sources
Leader creativity expectations	My supervisor expects me to be creative. Leaders want me to complete my work creatively. I know my leader is closely watching my creativity and matching it with my capacity. According to my previous performance leader anticipated me to solve the existing problem with creativity. My leader is like my guardian to me so by any means I need to prove myself as creative.	Carmeli and Schaubroeck (2007)
Creative Self-efficacy	I believe my skills will bring more innovative ideas. I am confident in my capacity to find creative solutions to problems. I always admire to enrich my knowledge bank by self-improvement My Feel reluctant to follow old fashion to solve my problems	Tierney and Farmer (2002) and Gong et al. (2009)
Paradoxical Leader Behaviour	The leader adopts an equitable approach to treat all subordinates fairly while recognizing their individuality. The leader ensures all subordinates are treated equally but takes their unique traits or personalities into account. The supervisor communicates consistently with all subordinates without bias but adjusts their communication style based on individual characteristics or needs. The leader manages subordinates equally while also considering their specific needs. The leader demonstrates a willingness to lead but also encourages others to participate in leadership roles..	Lewis, 2000; Smith & Lewis, 2011
Workload pressure	How much do you work in addition and hard to meet a deadline? Have you extra work to do? I also have to distinguish between alternative solutions	Bakker et al. (2004) and Miron-Spektor et al. (2018).
Employee Radical creativity	This subordinate suggests innovative ideas. He is not merely making slight adjustments to current research, workflows, products, or services. This subordinate puts forward highly original concepts. This employee can think out of the box and making our traditional operation system obsolete.	Madjar et al. (2011) and Baer (2012)

Control variables

The study found a variety of specific control variables, including education (PhD=3, Graduate, 1= Undergraduate), experience, dyadic tenure (in years), innovative career necessity, leadership support, and work freedom. Education is correlated with cognitive learning through the use of complex schemes, varied interactions and skills that allow people to feel secure in solving challenges creatively and exhibit ingenuity at work. Supervisor service line can impact subordinates' understanding of performance ratings for the supervisor (internal consistency 0.85). The study controlled for reflecting task domain knowledge measured on an item scale adopted from Unsworth & Engle (2005). Job autonomy is one of the sources of intrinsic motivation and may influence employees' end behaviour (Zhou & Oldham, 2004). As our sample is different in terms of job autonomy, we controlled it. Job autonomy is measured based on three items collected from the Spreitzer et al. sample. The items are “Do I have substantial rights and independence?”, “how I do my job?” with internal consistency (0.88). Leaders supporting behaviour generally influence employees' incremental or radical creativity (Tienery & Farmar, 2002). Therefore, we also control leaders' supportive behaviour along with conventional control variables like age, organisational and dyadic tenure. However, these variables did not modify our findings.

Multivariate assumption

After analysing the data, we can decide which statistical tests to use to review the dataset and determine whether the multivariate assumptions are fulfilled. Using Pearson's skewness and kurtosis statistics, we first compared the data distribution; the ideal values fell between -2.58 and +2.58. The conclusion that the data is normally distributed was made possible by the data analysis, which showed that the variable values were within the permissible range.

We used the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) test to investigate the non-linear correlations in more detail. These correlations were indeed linear, according to the OLS test's p-values (see Table 6).

Table 6: OLS Test

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	177.161	1	177.161	376.297	.000 ^b
	Residual	277.000	339	0.817		
a. DV: ERC						
b. Predictors: (Constant), LCE						
1	Regression	81.454	1	81.454	128.677	.000 ^b
	Residual	373.478	339	1.102		
a. DV: ERC						
b. Predictors: (Constant), PLB						
1	Regression	135.648	1	135.648	250.662	.000 ^b
	Residual	319.284	339	0.942		
a. DV: ERC						
b. Predictors: (Constant), WL						
1	Regression	175.010	1	175.010	368.873	.000 ^b
	Residual	279.922	339	0.826		
a. DV: ERC						
b. Predictors: (Constant), ECS						
1	Regression	143.776	1	143.776	306.358	.000 ^b
	Residual	276.892	339	0.817		
a. DV: ECS						
b. Predictors: (Constant), LCE						
1	Regression	62.076	1	62.076	102.135	.000 ^b
	Residual	358.592	339	1.058		
a. DV: ECS						
b. Predictors: (Constant), PLB						
1	Regression	95.056	1	95.056	172.238	.000 ^b
	Residual	325.612	339	0.961		
a. DV: ECS						
b. Predictors: (Constant), WL						

Notes: LCE= Leaders creativity expectations, PLB= Paradoxical leaders' behaviour, WL= Workload, ERC= Employees radical creativity.

In addition, the multicollinearity test satisfies the data set to move for further analysis (Table 7).

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Table 7: Test of Multicollinearity

Coefficients			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	LEC	.37	2.72
	PLB	.55	1.82
	WL	.52	1.94
	ECS	.65	1.55
a. Dependent Variable: ERC			

□

Notes: LCE= Leaders creativity expectations, PLB= Paradoxical leaders' behaviour, WL= Workload pressure, ERC= Employee's radical creativity.

Common Method Bias

We carefully worded questions to prevent ambiguity. CMB was detected statistically using various tests. We utilized Harman's one-factor technique and main axis factor analysis (PAF) to discover the number of components substantially contributing to variation (Harman, 1976). The results of the test suggested that a single construct was responsible for 29.08 per cent of the total variance, which is far below than the recommended 50 percent (Podsakoff, 2003).

Figure 2. Scree plots of variance

Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics

Table 9 shows scale reliabilities, correlations, and descriptive statistics. A favourable link exists between leaders' creativity expectations and workers' creative self-efficacy ($r = 0.21, p < .001$). Additionally, creative self-efficacy positively correlates with radical creativity ($r = 0.45, p < .01$). The control variables, education, organisational tenure, dyadic tenure, leader support, and work autonomy, are all strongly linked to at least one of our independent variables; thus, controlling for them makes sense.

Table 9: Descriptive statistics and correlations

	Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	Gender ^a	0.55	0.50												
2	Age ^b	35.38	9.28	-0.06											
3	Education ^c	2.58	1.04	0.08	.20**										
4	Org.Tenure ^d	12.82	9.81	0.01	.12*	0.10									
5	Dyadic Tenure ^e	4.52	0.99	-0.08	.17**	.11*	0.01								
6	leaders support	5.01	0.94	0.01	0.10	.11*	0.02	-0.04	(0.85)						
7	Job autonomy	4.86	0.96	-0.04	.13*	0.00	.12*	-0.07	.32**	(0.88)					
8	PLB	5.02	0.74	0.04	.17**	-0.06	0.03	-0.08	.34**	.25**	(0.89)				
9	LCE	5.00	0.85	-0.02	0.03	0.09	.11*	.110*	.23**	.34**	.37**	(0.91)			
10	Workload Pressure	4.60	1.04	-0.09	0.01	0.09	.003	0.04	.26**	.33**	.38**	.13**	(0.79)		
11	CSE	5.31	0.89	.11*	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.03	.36**	.26**	.49**	.21***	.45**	(0.84)	
12	ERC	5.05	0.75	.11*	.14**	0.03	.007	-0.04	.30**	.34**	.21**	.31***	.29**	.45**	(0.93)

* $P < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$; Two-tailed tests.

Notes: N =340. Cronbach’s Alpha in Parentheses on the diagonal. ^a0=Female, 1 = male. ^bAge, dyadic tenure^c and organizational tenure^d were measured in years. Education level is coded as 4 = Post doc, 3 = PhD. 2 = Master, 1 = Undergraduate. PLB= paradoxical leaders’ behaviour, LCE = leaders creativity expectations, CSE = creative self-efficacy, ERC = employee radical creativity

Confirmatory factor analysis

We assessed concept discriminant validity using maximum likelihood estimation in a series of confirmatory studies, as shown in **Table 10**. The hypothesised five-factor model is compared to four others. The four-factor model, which combines leaders' creativity expectations with paradoxical behaviour. The three-factor model combines leaders' creative expectations, paradoxical behaviour, and workload pressure. The two-factor model merged leaders' creativity expectations, paradoxical behaviour, workload pressure, and creative self-efficacy into one component. Finally, the one-factor model combined all five components into one.

Table 10: Comparison of Measurement Model

Model	χ^2	df	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
Five-factor ^a	1164	540	2.1	0.91	0.92	0.05
Four-factor ^b	2260	542	4.17	0.73	0.75	0.09
Three-factor ^c	2555	541	4.72	0.65	0.68	0.11
Two-factor ^d	3165	544	5.81	0.53	0.54	0.13
One-factor ^e	4629	554	8.35	0.51	0.47	0.14

Notes: CFI= Comparative fit index; TLI= Tucker-Lewis index; RMSEA= Root mean square error of approximation. ^a = Hypothesized five-factor model. ^b Leaders' creativity expectations and leaders' paradoxical behaviour are combined into one factor. ^c= Leaders creativity expectations, Paradoxical behavior and workload pressure are combined in to one factor. ^d= Leaders' creativity expectations, Paradoxical

behaviour, workload pressure and creative self-efficacy are combined into one factor. e = All five factors are combined into one factor.

Since workers were nested inside supervisors, we evaluated CSE and radical creativity across supervisors. With an ICC (1) of 0.05, group-level CSE variance was modest. Conversely, group-level radical creative variance was substantial (ICC (1) = 0.19, $p < .001$). To account for group-level effects, we used multilevel modelling with random leader intercepts. To simplify interpretation and eliminate multicollinearity, we grand mean-centered all variables except 'CSE' and 'ERC' before analysis (West & Aiken, 2003). We tested all hypotheses using Mplus with maximum likelihood estimation (Muthen, 2012).

Test of Hypothesis

The LCE, PLB and workload pressures have an interactive impact on ERC, as per Hypothesis 1, Table 11 which implies that when PLB and workload burden are both high, LCE has the greatest beneficial effect on ERC. The results indicate a significant three-way interaction among leader creativity expectations (LCE), paradoxical leadership behavior (PLB), and workload pressure on employee radical creativity (ERC) ($B = 0.27$, $SE = 0.11$, $p < .05$). Table 4 and Figure 2 show that LCE enhances creative self-efficacy (CSE) when task pressure and PLB are high ($B = 0.22$, $SE = 0.10$, $p < .05$). LCE negatively impacts CSE when paired with PLB and task strain. A substantial negative impact occurs when PLB is strong and task pressure is low ($B = -0.35$, $SE = 0.12$, $p < .01$). This supports the idea that LCE is less meaningful when PLB is minimal since its impacts were negligible. This supports hypothesis 1.

To investigate the three-way interaction, we investigated PLB simple slopes under various LCE and workload pressure combinations. The study found that PLB positively impacted CSE only when LCE and workload pressure were high ($B = 0.20$, $SE = 0.09$, $p < 0.05$). PLB had no significant influence on CSE when LCE and workload pressure were low ($B = 0.08$, $SE = 0.06$, ns), high and low ($B = -0.07$, $SE = 0.10$, ns), or low and high ($B = -0.20$, $SE = 0.10$, $p < 0.10$). According to paradoxical theory, stressful events may enhance learning, and paradoxical leaders' behavior positively affect CSE, but only for high-workload workers who may benefit from their bosses' creative demands.

In hypothesis 2, creative self-efficacy (CSE) mediates the conditional impact of leader creativity expectations (LCE) on workers' radical creativity, with the positive indirect effect of LCE being highest when paradoxical leadership behavior (PLB) and workload pressure are high. Table 5 shows multilevel modelling findings. After adjusting for factors and LCE, CSE remained a significant predictor of radical creativity ($B = 0.30$, $SE = 0.08$, $p < .01$). The Monte Carlo bootstrapping method (Preacher, 2012) showed that LCE positively impacted radical creativity only when PLB and workload pressure were high ($B = 0.08$, $SE = 0.04$, $p < .05$, 95% CI [0.01, 0.15]). In contrast, LCE exhibited a significant negative indirect impact with high PLB and low workload pressure ($B = -0.11$, $SE = 0.05$, $p < .05$, 95% CI [-0.23, -0.03]). LCE indirectly affected radical creativity negatively but not significantly when PLB and workload pressure were low, as well as when workload pressure was high and PLB was low. We computed the simple slopes with

the values of the moderators at on standard deviation above and below the mean. These result support Hypothesis 2.

Table 12: Conditional effect of LCE on creative self-efficacy

Comparison	Slop	t
(High PLB, high WL) 1, A	0.22 (0.10)	2.47*
(Low PLB, low WL) 2, B	-0.22 (0.11)	1.76
(Low PLB, high WL) 3, C	-0.23 (0.13)	-1.55
(High PLB, low WL) 4, D	-0.35 (0.12)	-2.83**
<i>Differences of slope</i>		
A and B	0.45 (0.14)	3.05**
A and C	0.47 (0.18)	2.47*
A and D	0.59 (0.14)	4.23***
B and C	0.01 (0.19)	0.05
B and D	0.15 (0.15)	0.79
C and D	0.13 (0.20)	0.62
Notes: Standard errors are in parentheses. N=340. *p <.05, **p <.01, ***p <.001		

Table 13: Multilevel modelling results for the moderated mediation model

Control Variables	Dependent Variable	
	Creative self-efficacy	Employee Radical Creativity
Education Level	0.06 (0.04)	0.18**(0.05)
Dyadic Tenure	-0.04 (0.01)	-0.04(0.01)
Job autonomy	0.05 (0.05)	0.02(0.01)
Leaders Support	0.05 (0.04)	0.07(0.06)
Predictors		
Leaders creativity expectations (LCE)	-0.17*(0.07)	-0.04(0.09)
Paradoxical leader behaviour (PLB)	0.00 (0.05)	
Workload Pressure (WL)	0.38***(0.09)	
Interaction terms		
LCE*PLB	0.09 (0.06)	
LCE*WL	0.26*(0.11)	
WL*PLB	0.00 (0.07)	
LCE*PLB*WL	0.25*(0.10)	
Mediator		
Creative self-efficacy (CSE)		0.30**(0.08)

Notes: N=340, standard errors are shown in parentheses.
 p < .10, *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

Table 14: Indirect effects (Conditional effects) of LCE on Employee Radical Creativity through CSE

	Effect	95% confidence interval
1 (High PLB, high WL)	0.08*(0.04)	[0.01,0.15]
2 (Low PLB, low WL)	0.08 (0.03)	[0.15,0.01]
3 (Low PLB, high WL)	-0.08 (0.04)	[0.17,0.03]
4 (High PLB, low WL)	-0.11 (0.05)	[-0.23, -0.03]

Notes. N= 340 standard errors are in parentheses. The confidence interval for the indirect effect was constructed with the Monte Carlo method (20,000 repetitions)
 The study computed the conditional indirect effect with the values of the moderators At one stand deviation above and below the mean.

Figure 3. Three-way interaction among LCE, PLB and workload pressure on Creative self-efficacy.

Discussion

These discoveries affect various scientific fields. First, this research explains how leaders may foster creative self-efficacy (CSE) and inventive thinking in stressed personnel. Previous studies have shown that leadership style affects CSE and creativity, reducing the negative effects of job fatigue on employee well-being, motivation, and organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB). However, little is known about what boosts CSE and radical creativity under difficult situations. In addition, while leader behaviour affects follower performance depending on contextual factors like follower stress, research suggests that follower stress reduces the relationship between empowering leadership and follower performance. We discovered that leaders' creative expectations promoted CSE and radical creativity, especially among workers under high workload pressure and receiving contradictory leadership. LCE was ineffective when workload pressure was low and even hurt CSE and radical creativity when PLB was low and workload pressure was high. Thus, our study illuminates how leaders may boost radical innovation in high-pressure workplaces. The following sections describe how this work enhances the literature theoretically and practically.

Theoretical Implications

Our investigation into the interplay of Leaders' Creativity Expectations (LCE), creative self-efficacy (CSE), and radical creativity enhances the growing corpus of research about the influence of expectations on creativity. Our research examined the interaction of leaders' creative expectations, leaders' behaviour, and environmental circumstances, illustrating their combined influence on CSE and radical creativity. Our results indicate that paradoxical leaders, by the demonstration of opposing but interconnected behaviour, may augment employee CSE, hence facilitating the management of substantial tensions (Zhang et al., 2015); this impact is especially pertinent for workers under considerable workload strain. Our study is one of the few that links paradoxical leadership with studies on radical innovation.

we discerned two significant boundary conditions influencing the efficacy of LCE on CSE and creativity. This emphasis on the paradoxical behavior of leaders and contextual elements such as workload pressure diverges from the prevailing research on paradoxes, which often neglects individual variances and organizational circumstances (Schad et al., 2016). Our study indicates that investigations into paradoxical leadership should examine the particular circumstances that may influence the positive or negative effects of PLB on creative performance. For example, we discovered that LCE may impede CSE when people do not experience the requisite workload pressure to accept and embrace it; in such instances, paradoxical leaders may be seen as unpleasant, uncomfortable, and perplexing. This corresponds with Zhang et al. (2015)'s claim that leaders should acknowledge workers' openness to paradoxes while exhibiting complex and seemingly conflicting behavior. This study further enhances the contributions of Miron-Spektor et al. (2018) on the micro-foundations of organizational paradoxes, emphasizing the significance of paradoxical thinking in resolving disputes stemming from resource scarcity. Current evidence suggests that PLB functions as a double-edged sword, promoting employee radical innovation just under certain settings.

Practical Implications

Our research offers empirical evidence that Leaders' Creativity Expectations (LCE) and paradoxical leadership behaviour (PLB)—particularly behaviour that amalgamate external performance expectations, control, autonomy, constraints, and flexibility—can augment employee creative self-efficacy (CSE) and radical creativity in high workload contexts. Although several scholars suggest that paradoxical leadership may enhance innovation and creativity, actual data substantiating this claim is limited. While research has shown that leaders can effectively integrate conflicting behaviour (Zacher & Rosing, 2015) and contrasting personal characteristics (such as leader narcissism and humility, Owens, Wallace, & Waldman, 2015) to improve follower performance, none of this literature has explicitly focused on radical creativity.

Moreover, managers might augment creative self-efficacy (CSE) by adeptly managing workplace difficulties. Initially, they may assist their subordinates in comprehending that divergent objectives and methodologies associated with radical innovation can be harmonised and synthesised. Managers may mentor staff to accept these expectation-driven objectives and adopt contradictory behaviour. Moreover, they may provide a work climate that harmonises autonomy with structure, offering people both direction and the liberty to participate in creative endeavours, thus enhancing CSE and radical innovation. By exemplifying good behaviour and cultivating a supportive environment for managing expectations, tensions, and pressures, leaders may mitigate anxiety and stress among workers confronting paradoxical obstacles in radical innovation. This research underscores that cultivating creative self-efficacy entails not just encouraging radical innovation but also adeptly navigating the contradictory hurdles inherent in substantial creative pursuits.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

The data were gathered from various sites; our cross-sectional survey data does not eliminate the possibility of reverse causality. For instance, it's plausible that more creative employees might inspire leaders to adopt more paradoxical behavior. Despite this limitation, our field data supports the external validity of the conceptual model. Future research should examine the internal

applicability of our model by testing PLB in a controlled laboratory setting or by utilizing longitudinal designs. Additionally, since the three-way interaction effect was assessed based on evidence from a single study, the common method variance is unlikely to inflate the reported interaction effect. In fact, Siemsen et al. (2010) argued that identifying significant interaction effects amidst potential common method variance should be considered strong evidence of the proposed interaction effect.

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